

A DATASCOPE FOR SATELLITE DATA

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ABSTRACT

The Copernicus program will produce a sizable stream of remote sensor data, which when combined with ground sensor systems provides a fertile soil to explain the past and predict the future of Planet Earth's health. The sheer size and data complexity calls for innovative technology to provide efficient and effective data exploration.

We present a DataScope for Satellite data, a framework geared at interactive derivation of knowledge from various remote sensing data sources. It can handle their voluminous data sizes and geo-distribution. Moreover, it simplifies the task for the data scientist who wants to adapt his search parameters to steer his scientific quest. At the same time being able to browse the data stored in the Cloud, to execute complex algorithms, and correlate it with data stored at a different location.

Index Terms— Satellite data, Data Management, Data processing, DataScope

1. INTRODUCTION

The Copernicus program uses remote sensing to monitor the health of our planet. Remote sensing provides large area coverage for regional surveys, data acquisition at different scales and resolution, repetitive coverage, monitoring dynamic themes like water, forests, agriculture, etc. It shifts traditional field work into a digital lab work setting, much like most astronomers nowadays look at computer screens then through the lens of a telescope.

Remote sensing data is more than just spectral, spatial and temporal information. Its size, complexity and diversity will increase by orders of magnitude in the coming decade as more sentinels are launched to space and combined with ground surface sensors data. Furthermore, it is designed to serve different consumers: scientists, municipalities, companies, or home users. Data exploration will occur at different resolutions with an user collecting an insight or submitting a job for a precise answer.

The pivotal technologies to achieve results are Database Management Systems (DBMSs), they are used on science work-flows on institutional compute clusters or within the public cloud. Unfortunately, most DBMSs considered for Earth Observation (EO) share three major drawbacks: static

storage model, data ownership, and lack of support for step wise data exploration [1]. One might argue that the NoSQL class of databases, such as Cassandra and HBase or MapReduce frameworks [2] are less restrictive to the change of focus by the Data Scientists. The caveat, however, is that they call for strong programming experience to harvest the potential performance. The model is mostly effective for single scan, cleanup, and summarization tasks. The trend to align NoSQL and SQL systems is proven by product offerings such as BigInsights¹ and Pivotal².

A traditional approach is to rely on specialized libraries which are mostly file based systems, rich in functionality and created by domain experts. However, they suffer from data isolation and applications become dependent on data formats and humans software skills. They are known for their poor scalability, e.g. on multi-core computers, and data interchange between different libraries is tedious. Standardization of e.g. HDF5 leaves many options open for a domain expert to encode his information. It is this freedom that often make re-use of the data by others a daunting programming task.

A leapfrogging experience will come from fusing data from different sources into a single data exploration framework. Such a framework should be resilient over time, adopting and evolving with the data received, and stimulate research insights for a broad spectrum user community. Hence, EO data science requires a scientific instrument capable of seeing what the data management tools and specialized libraries cannot. In Science and Industrial literature such an instrument is referenced as DataScope [3, 4].

With a DataScope, raw data from our environment is extracted and organized before being massaged by a set of tools to extract information [4]. It provides fast data ingestion and a guided dynamic step wise exploration in those "heterogeneous mountains of data", i.e., the bottom layer of new data science instruments for data exploration.

In short paper we will present our DataScope for remote sensing data. It creates a true symbiosis between the best of bread open-source columnar database system, specialized libraries, and programming languages (R, Python, Java, C).

¹<http://www-01.ibm.com/software/data/infosphere/biginsights/>

²<http://blog.gopivotal.com/tag/hawq>

2. A DATASCOPE ECOSYSTEM

With a DataScope raw data from our environment is extracted and organized before being massaged by a set of tools to extract knowledge. Its novelty is visible in three key-areas.

2.1. Data access

The DataScope is designed to efficiently combine heterogeneous data sets while providing *in-situ* data access, i.e., it keeps data in its original format while scalable and distributed processing functionality is offered through a DBMS. It provides transparent access to all data kept in the file repository through a tabular or array-based interface abstraction [5].

The *in-situ* data access is possible due to the large amounts of metadata (data of data) existent on file formats such as NetCDF, LAS/LAZ, MSEEDS, HDF5, etc. Such metadata is used for effective data skipping, but also to collect data insights, e.g. summaries and samples, without having to process the entire data set. It is treated as rough sets which allows us to use machine learning techniques for clustering and approximated answers [6]. Combined with statistical models and equations they are a compressed form for data representation.

Such an approach gives the user the opportunity to continue performing data curation activities since the main data archive is the file-based repository, i.e., the raw data is kept outside of the DBMS. The data imported into the DBMS is easily invalidated in case of updates. For a new data format version the catalog tables are easily updatable and a new data loader is provided.

The dynamic data loading comprises of three phases: the attachment of a file, the import of the file's content and the collection of statistics to boost query optimization. During the attachment, the file's metadata is loaded into a special DBMS catalog. At query time, such a catalog is inspected to decide whether the file has information relevant to the query or not. In such a case the file's content is imported into the database.

The data import happens in two flavors, if the file format has each attribute sequentially stored then the import memory maps each attribute as a column, otherwise, the data is converted and loaded into the database as temporary data. In the latter case, cache policies, such as Least Recently Used (LRU), are used for data eviction.

To improve data parallelism, during the import one or more relational tables are created. These tables are seen as partitions and they are glued using a *merge table* to hide the data partition from the user (c.f., Figure 1). The following SQL code shows the attachment of files under a sub-directory to each partition, the creation of a merge table and the addition of partitions to it.

```
call attachDir('tab1', <dir_path>);  
...  
call attachDir('tabN', <dir_path>);
```


Fig. 1. Merge Table

```
create merge table observations  
  (id bigint, x real, y real, z real);  
  
1) alter table observation add table tab1;  
...  
N) alter table observation add table tabN;
```

2.2. Data processing

At the heart of our DataScope there is a modern column-store, MonetDB [7], which steps away from traditional relational database management systems (RDBMS). Through vertical partitioning of relational tables column-store significantly reduce data access. In our case, vertical partitioning is exploited to reduce the number of columns to be imported. Such data organization improves data compression, simplifies data skipping strategies and it suits well vector processing.

On top, a column-store provides efficient secondary indices for in-memory filtering. In the filtering step, the majority of the queries are range selections. Such type of filtering is speed up using secondary indexes such as column imprints [8]. Column-imprints resembles bitmaps that index ranges of values in each cache line of each column. This makes them very efficient in range queries since they allow skipping cache lines that do not contain data for a desired range. Hence, an imprint is used during query evaluation to limit data access, and thus minimize memory traffic. The compression of imprints is CPU friendly and exploits the empirical observation that data often exhibits local clustering or partial ordering as a side effect of the construction process such as in the EO data collection process.

A coarser grain filtering is achieved through partition elimination which happens at query compilation time. During query compilation, the predicates are inspected and compared with statistical information collected for each partition. Such information is obtained from the file's header, by sampling, or simply by running an analyze call. For the partitions shown

in Figure 1, the following SQL code is used to collect the minimum and maximum value for columns x , y , and z of each partition.

```
analyze sys.tab1 (x, y, z) minmax;
...
analyze sys.tabN (x, y, z) minmax;
```

For example, a range selection such as x between 51.5 and 54.5 and y between 3.75 and 7.75 the query plan will only request the scan of partitions within the 2D bounding box.

2.3. Data distilling

Our DataScope provides a powerful, seamless integration for handling declarative data (SQL), statistics and learning (R), image/timeseries analysis (SciQL). As a last resort, domain specific libraries can be easily linked with the system. R is used to express statistical analysis, simple geographic summaries, and for visualization. N-dimensional array based functions are expressed through SciQL. SQL as declarative language is ideal to express complex ad-hoc queries and data flows, it has been extended with support for the objects and functions defined in the specification of the Simple Feature Specification of the Open Geo-spatial Consortium(OGC)³.

2.3.1. New functionality

The architecture is designed following a modular approach where new functionality is easily incorporated through new operators or with a seamless integration of specialized libraries. The integration of new functionality follows three steps with each of them related with each MonetDB layer, i.e., front-end layer, intermediate layer (optimization layer), and kernel.

The first step is to expose the new functionality to the user using a SQL procedure or function. The second step is to define the operator for the intermediate query plan represented in MonetDB Assembly Language (MAL). Such operator is interpreted by the DBMS optimizers as an internal operator, and thus considered in all the optimization strategies. The final step happens at the Kernel where a C function is defined and which is linked to the MAL operator at runtime.

```
SQL:
create procedure listDir(dirPath string)
    external name eo.listdir;
MAL:
module eo;
pattern listdir(dirname:str):void
address eoListDir
C:
void eoListDir(
    Client cntxt, MalBlkPtr mb,
    MalStkPtr stk, InstrPtr pci);
```

³<http://www.opengeospatial.org/>

2.3.2. External environments

Our solution exploits the fact that deep integration of external environments, such as R and Python, are easy to implement in MonetDB. In the case of R environment, used for statistical computing [9], statistical analyses are integrated through a MonetDB.R client program [10].

Through the R dplyr package MonetDB.R [10] filtering, grouping, and aggregation operations are pushed into the database for execution and only the result is moved to the R environment. This way, large amounts of data can be inspected and filtered out before transferring it to the R front-end to identify, for instance, correlations.

Load and filter a DBMS table from R

```
01: /* load libraries */
02: library(dplyr)
03: library(MonetDB.R)
04:
05: /* Connect to database netcdf */
06: src <- src_monetdb("earth.observation")
07:
08: /* Load table */
09: tbl1 <- tbl(src, "cum_prec")
10:
11: /* Apply filters */
12: tbl2 <- filter(tbl1, lat > 51.5, lat < 54.5)
13: tbl3 <- filter(tbl2, lon > 3.75, lon < 7.75)
14:
15: /* Sort data */
16: tbl4 <- filter(tbl3, desc(prec))
17:
18: /* Push down the query and collect result */
19: cumprecdf <- collect(tbl4)
```

Fig. 2. R code

The R code in Figure 2 shows how to connect to a DBMS instance hosting *earth_observation* database and retrieve all cumulative precipitation for a 2D bounding box defined between latitude 51.5 and 54.5 and longitude between 3.75 and 7.75. Using dplyr, the R statements on *line 09* specify the table to be accessed, the bounding box range selection is done with statements on *line 12 and 13* while the sorting of the result is done on *line 16*. Once the collect statement on *line 19* is issued, these statements are pushed down to the DBMS, optimized, and executed.

Load and filter a DBMS table from SQL

```
01: select * from cum.prectbl1
02: where
03: lat between 51 and 50.0
04: and lon between 3.75 and 7.75
05: order by prec DESC
```

Fig. 3. SQL code

Such statements are equivalent to the SQL query in Figure 3. In Figure 3 the table identification is done on *line 01*, the range selections on *line 03 and 04* while the sorting is covered by *line 05*.

2.4. A vision in action

Our DataScope ecosystem has emerged through a decade of support for scientific data management and adheres to the vision expressed in [1, 11]. It stands on the shoulders of previous experience on building solutions for remote sensing data processing. A snippet of the history in two domains:

Astronomy We developed our solution by providing an alternative implementation for the *The Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS)*, which aims to map one third for the sky to obtain observations of 100 million objects. Subsequently, the technique was included in the Dutch LOFAR radio telescope software stack, and is currently researched in the context of an Amazon supported project for the Square Kilometer Array telescope.

Remote sensing Our DataScope efficiency was shown with several use cases, ranging heat islands detection for urban planning [11] using LIDAR, cadastral data and ground based sensor data as the data substrate, to satellite image analysis for forest fire detection and precision farming⁴. It facilitated the integration of different heterogeneous data sets for exploration in four dimensions, 3D space and time. It provided flexible and efficient analysis of spatiotemporal data.

In [11] large NetCDF file repositories were attached as well as a large LiDAR file repository. Using MonetDBs R front-end the data sets were explored in search of heat islands at Rotterdam city center. The focus was on the monthly temperature average difference for February 2015 at 4PM. With our DataScope in-situ data access spatiotemporal data referring to Rotterdam city center and February temperature measurements were imported from the attached file repositories. The imported data was then aggregated and sorted before being passed to the R environment. See Figure 2.4.

Step-wise exploration is thus at the distance of a click. A simple zoom-out interaction by the user on his/her web-browser will trigger a chained reaction which would propagate from the R interface all the way down to a data import from the file repositories attached to the DBMS.

3. SUMMARY

In our experience, knowledge and deployment of modern scientific database technology and software technology is a *sine qua non* to push the data science envelop of EO. We shortly introduced a DataScope for remote sensing which provides the means to access and combine geographical data through interlinked data hubs (snippets as data representation), integration and fusion of sensor data, and metadata management to improve data processing.

Our solution combines the best of both file-based and database management systems (open-source) technologies.

⁴EU Projects, e.g. TELEIOS <http://www.earthobservatory.eu>
<http://www.linkedeodata.eu/>

Fig. 4. Rotterdam city center [11]

For data access it efficiently combines heterogeneous data sets while providing in-situ data access. For data processing it exploits external accelerators (HPC and HTC) to accelerate computations. For data exploration its modular architecture allows the integration of specialized functionality without downgrading data processing efficiency.

The results are presented through interactive front-ends and provided as service for downstream data dissemination. Each layer is coupled in seamless way to have shorter times between data acquisition and data presentation.

4. REFERENCES

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